

AXBOROTLASHGAN JAMIYATI

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Ijtimoiy gumanitar fanlar kafedrasida o'qituvchisi

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Annotatsiya. Hozirgi davr axborot oqimlari hajmining misli ko'rilmagan o'sishi bilan tavsiflangan davrdir. Bu iqtisodiyotga ham, ijtimoiy sohaga ham tegishli. Axborot texnologiya va umuman resurslarning rivojlanishini belgilovchi hal qiluvchi omil hisoblanadi. Bozor munosabatlari axborotning o'z vaqtida bo'lishi, ishonchliligi va to'liqligiga talablarni oshiradi. Jamiyatni axborotlashtirishning asosiy tushunchalaridan biri "axborot resurslari" tushunchasiga aylandi.

Kalit so'zlar: axborot, oqim, kompyuter, rivojlanish.

INFORMATION SOCIETY

Abstract. The current period is characterized by an unprecedented increase in the volume of information flows. This applies to both the economy and the social sphere. Information is a decisive factor determining the development of technology and resources in general. Market relations increase requirements for timeliness, reliability and completeness of information. One of the main concepts of public information has become the concept of "information resources".

Key words: information, flow, computer, development.

ИНФОРМАЦИОННОЕ ОБЩЕСТВО

Аннотация. Современный период характеризуется беспрецедентным ростом объёмов информационных потоков. Это касается как экономики, так и социальной сферы. Информация является решающим фактором, определяющим развитие технологий и ресурсов в целом. Рыночные отношения повышают требования к своевременности, достоверности и полноте информации. Одним из основных понятий общественной информации стало понятие «информационные ресурсы».

Ключевые слова: информация, поток, компьютер, развитие.

Zamonaviy jamiyatda juda ko'p sonli kompyuterlar va umuman, turli xil axborot texnologiyalari (telefonlar, televizorlar, fakslar va boshqalar) mavjud. Ma'lumotni qidirish, saqlash va o'zgartirish bilan bog'liq ko'plab kasblar mavjud. Axborot iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy rivojlanishning hal qiluvchi resursiga aylanmoqda. Axborotlashtirish deganda faqat eng yangi kompyuter, telekommunikatsiya texnologiyalari va Internet negizida zamonaviy kompyuter va axborot texnologiyalarini inson va jamiyat hayotiga joriy etish jarayoni tushuniladi, xolos. Axborotlashtirish jarayonining mohiyati va mazmuni nimada? Axborotlashtirish - axborot jamiyatini yaratish va shu asosda tsivilizatsiya taraqqiyotini yanada davom ettirish maqsadida informatika vositalaridan foydalangan holda axborotni boshqarish va rivojlantirish manbasi sifatida o'zlashtirish jarayoni.

Axborot jamiyati sivilizatsiya rivojlanishining yangi tarixiy bosqichi bo'lib, unda ishlab chiqarishning asosiy mahsuloti axborot va bilim hisoblanadi.

Axborot jamiyatining asosiy xususiyatlari:

1. Axborot va bilimlarning jamiyat hayotidagi rolini oshirish.

2. Axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari sohasida band bo'lganlar sonining ko'payishi.
3. Yalpi ichki mahsulotda axborot mahsulotlari va xizmatlari ulushini oshirish.
4. Jamiyat ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, siyosiy va madaniy hayotining barcha jabhalarida AKTdan keng miqyosda foydalanish.
5. Global axborot makonini yaratish.
6. Axborot iqtisodiyoti, elektron hukumat, elektron ijtimoiy tarmoqlar va boshqalarni rivojlantirish.

Hozirgi davr axborot oqimlari hajmining misli ko'rilmagan o'sishi bilan tavsiflangan davrdir. Bu iqtisodiyotga ham, ijtimoiy sohaga ham tegishli. Axborot texnologiya va umuman resurslarning rivojlanishini belgilovchi hal qiluvchi omil hisoblanadi. Bozor munosabatlari axborotning o'z vaqtida bo'lishi, ishonchliligi va to'liqligiga talablarni oshiradi. Jamiyatni axborotlashtirishning asosiy tushunchalaridan biri "axborot resurslari" tushunchasiga aylandi.

Insoniyat tomonidan fan, madaniyat, ta'lim va odamlarning amaliy faoliyati rivojlanishi jarayonida to'plangan barcha ma'lumotlar yig'indisi axborot resurslari deb ataladi.

Axborot resursi fayl, hujjat, veb-sayt, fotosurat, videoklip bo'lishi mumkin. Axborot resursi - foydalanuvchi muammolarini hal qilish uchun qayta ishlatilishi mumkin bo'lgan har qanday shakldagi ma'lumotlar. Davlat axborot resurslari davlat boshqaruvi muammolarini hal qilish, fuqarolarning huquqlari va xavfsizligini ta'minlash, mamlakatning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishini qo'llab-quvvatlash, madaniyat, fan, ta'lim va boshqalarni rivojlantirish uchun ishlatiladi. Davlat axborot tizimlaridagi ma'lumotlar federal qonunlarga bo'ysunadi. "Axborot, axborot texnologiyalari va axborotni muhofaza qilish to'g'risida" gi qonun.

Jamiyatning axborot resurslarini insoniyat tomonidan to'plangan va hujjatlar, ma'lumotlar bazalari, bilimlar bazalari, algoritmlar, kompyuter dasturlari, san'at, adabiyot va fanlar ko'rinishida moddiylashtirilgan bilimlar deb hisoblash mumkin.

Axborot resurslarini quyidagicha tasniflash mumkin:

- Kutubxona resurslari.
- Arxiv manbalari.
- Ilmiy va texnik ma'lumotlar.
- Huquqiy ma'lumotlar va davlat organlarining ma'lumotlari.
- sanoat ma'lumotlari.
- Moliyaviy va iqtisodiy ma'lumotlar.
- Tabiiy resurslar haqida ma'lumot va boshqalar.

Axborot resurslari har qanday davlatda resurslarning eng muhim turlaridan biri sifatida tan olinadi. Eng rivojlangan mamlakatlarda ularga alohida e'tibor beriladi.

Hozirgi vaqtda moddiy mahsulot qiymatini pasaytirish jarayoni faol davom etmoqda, ammo axborotning qiymati ortib bormoqda. Zamonaviy jamiyatda axborot qimmatli mahsulotga aylanmoqda.

Axborot mahsuloti - mahsulot ko'rinishida taqdim etilgan, ya'ni pulga sotish yoki boshqa mahsulotlarga almashtirish maqsadida yaratilgan barcha turdagi ma'lumotlar, dasturiy mahsulotlar, ma'lumotlar bazalari.

Axborot mahsuloti universal avtomatlashtirish va axborotlashtirish davrining o'ziga xos ko'rsatkichi bo'lib, moddiy mahsulotdan bir qator ma'lum farqlarga ega. Shunday qilib, har qanday

axborot mahsuloti butun ma'lumotga xos bo'lgan sifatga ega - u eskirish yoki jismoniy eskirishga duchor bo'lmaydi. Axborot mahsulotidan qayta-qayta foydalanishingiz mumkin va u o'zining sifati va o'ziga xosligini yo'qotmaydi. Masalan: filmni bir necha marta o'ynash uning mazmuniga hech qanday ta'sir qilmaydi. Film har bir tomosha bilan yomonlashmaydi. Ammo shuni aytish kerakki, axborot mahsuloti eskirish deb ataladigan narsaga duchor bo'ladi.

Kecha dolzarb bo'lgan ma'lumotlar bugun o'zining barcha ahamiyatini va dolzarbligini yo'qotishi mumkin. Axborot mahsulotining yana bir indikativ xususiyati shundaki, uni ishlab chiqarish xarajatlari, qoida tariqasida, uni takrorlashning keyingi xarajatlaridan bir necha baravar yuqori. Noyob asarni bir marta yozish har doim uni minglab nusxalarga ko'paytirishdan ko'ra qiyinroqdir. Axborot mahsulotining muhim xususiyati uning maqsadlilikidir. Iste'molchi guruhiga qarab, ishlab chiqaruvchi kelajakdagi axborot mahsulotini ishlab chiqarish shakli va usulini tanlaydi. Shunday qilib, ilmiy ishning professional jamoada nashr etilishi bir xil ilmiy g'oyani maktab o'quvchilari uchun ommalashtirishdan farq qiladi. Axborot mahsuloti ko'p qirralilik xususiyatiga ega - u turli xil qo'llash sohalari uchun qimmatli bo'lishi mumkin, turli loyihalarda turli maqsadlarda foydalaniladi.

Axborot mahsulotlari axborot xizmatlari orqali tarqatiladi.

Axborot xizmati - bu axborot mahsulotlarini olish va foydalanuvchiga taqdim etishga qaratilgan odamlar va tashkilotlarning harakatlari.

Axborot xizmatlari har xil turlarda keladi, masalan: ma'lumotlarni qidirish va tanlash. Turli ishga yollash agentliklari ishga yollash xizmatlarini taqdim etadi. Axborot xizmatlariga turli o'quv markazlari, reklama agentliklari faoliyati, dasturlar va veb-saytlar ishlab chiqish kiradi.

Resurslar va mahsulotlarning an'anaviy turlarida bo'lgani kabi, odamlar axborot resurslari qayerda joylashganligini, ularning narxi qancha ekanligini, kimga tegishli ekanligini, kimga kerakligi va ulardan foydalanish qanchalik qulayligini bilishlari kerak. Axborot mahsulotlari va xizmatlari bozori mavjud bo'lsa, bu savollarga javob olish mumkin.

Axborot mahsulotlari va xizmatlari bozori (axborot bozori) - intellektual mehnat mahsulotlarini tijorat asosida sotish uchun iqtisodiy, huquqiy va tashkiliy munosabatlar tizimi.

Axborot bozorida beshta sektorni ajratish mumkin:

- sanoatning turli tarmoqlarida konstruktiv, texnologik, uslubiy ishlanmalar ko'rinishidagi *ilmiy-texnik mahsulotlar*;

- matn, tasvir va audio mahsulot ko'rinishidagi *badiiy madaniyat ob'ektlari*;

- *ta'lim xizmatlari*: o'qitishning barcha turlari;

- *boshqaruv ma'lumotlari va xabarlari*: siyosiy va iqtisodiy ma'lumotlar, statistik ma'lumotlar, bozor holati to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlar, reklama xabarlari, qarorlar qabul qilish uchun baholashlar va tavsiyalar;

- *uy xo'jaligi ma'lumotlari*: umumiy xabarlar, iste'mol bozori haqida ma'lumot, mehnat bozori haqida ma'lumot.

Axborot jamiyati sari intilayotganimiz sari ta'lim sohasida axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan foydalanish bilan bog'liq imkoniyatlarning ortib borishi paydo bo'lmoqda: maktablarni multimedia kompyuter texnikasi va fizika, kimyo, biologiya kabinetlari uchun raqamli laboratoriyalar bilan jihozlash; maktablarda media markazlarni shakllantirish; maktablarni internet tarmog'iga ulash; darslarda va uyda raqamli ta'lim resurslaridan foydalanish; ma'muriy

funksiyalarni avtomatlashtirish uchun individual ilovalardan foydalanish: kadrlar hisobi, maktab shtat jadvalini yuritish, dars jadvallarini tayyorlashda foydalanish, oliy ta'lim organlari bilan hujjatlar almashinuvi. Bu jarayonlarning barchasi ta'lim muassasalarida axborot-ta'lim muhiti shakllanganidan dalolat beradi. O'qitishda elektron ta'lim resurslaridan tobora ko'proq foydalanilmoqda, ular:

- o'rganilayotgan ob'yektlar haqidagi ma'lumotlarni modellashtirish va vizuallashtirish;
- foydalanuvchi va AKT vositalari o'rtasidagi interaktiv aloqa;
- katta hajmdagi axborotni ularga oson kirish imkoniyati bilan saqlash;
- hisoblash, axborot-qidiruv faoliyati jarayonlarini avtomatlashtirish, shuningdek, o'quv eksperimenti natijalarini parcha yoki tajribaning o'zini ko'p marta takrorlash imkoniyati bilan qayta ishlash;
- ta'lim faoliyatini tashkiliy boshqarish va o'quv natijalari monitoringini avtomatlashtirish;
- mahalliy va global kompyuter tarmoqlaridan foydalangan holda ta'lim jarayoni ishtirokchilarining axborot o'zaro ta'siri.

Suhbatdoshlaringizga muammo tug'dirmaslik va uning turli xil xizmatlaridan foydalangan holda Internetda muloqot qilishda muammoga duch kelmaslik uchun netiket deb ataladigan ba'zi oddiy qoidalarga amal qilish foydalidir. Netiket qoidalari oddiy va haqiqiy hayotdagi xatti-harakatlar qoidalariga o'xshaydi.

Chat, forum yoki telekonferentsiyada muloqot qilish uchun boshqa chat ishtirokchilarini xafa qilmaydigan taxallus yoki taxallusni tanlang. Ayol yoki erkak ekanligingizni anglatmaydigan neytral nomlardan saqlaning. Biror kishiga murojaat qilganingizda, iborangizning boshiga uning taxallusini yozing. Rasmiy yozishmalarda xat muallifi haqida ba'zi ma'lumotlarni o'z ichiga olgan imzodan foydalanish odatiy holdir: to'liq ism, lavozim yoki boshqa regaliya, aloqa ma'lumotlari. Ko'p hollarda elektron pochta dasturlari xat tayyor bo'lgach, unga avtomatik ravishda imzo qo'shib qo'yganligi sababli, imzoga barcha muxbirlaringizga ko'rsatishni istamaydigan ma'lumotlarni qo'ymaslikdan ehtiyot bo'ling.

Ko'p sonli odamlar chat, forum yoki mehmonlar kitobida turli fikrlar va qiziqishlar bilan muloqot qilishadi. Siz o'z bayonotlaringizda xushmuomala va to'g'ri bo'lishingiz kerak. Biror kishining fikri siznikiga to'g'ri kelmasa, unga hujum qilmang. Suhbatni tark etayotganda, suhbatdoshlaringiz bilan xayrlashishni unutmang va, ehtimol, keyingi suhbat vaqtini birgalikda kelishib oling.

Har doim elektron pochtagizning mavzu maydonini to'ldiring. Mavzularga e'tibor qaratib, kiruvchi yozishmalarning katta ro'yxatida kerakli harflarni tanlash, shuningdek, spamni (inglizcha spamdan) filtrlash osonroq - intruziv reklama. Birovning elektron pochtagiga javob berayotganda mavzu maydoniga Re: Asl mavzuni kiritish odatiy holdir. Ko'pgina elektron pochta dasturlari ushbu iborani avtomatik ravishda kiritadi.

Grammatik xatolardan qochishga harakat qiling. Ko'pgina zamonaviy matn protsessorlari va elektron pochta dasturlarida o'rnatilgan imlo tekshiruvi mavjud. Qanday bo'lmasin, xatni yuborishdan oldin uni qayta o'qib chiqish foydalidir. Xuddi shu iborani qayta-qayta takrorlamang, e'firga vaqt sarflamang.

Oddiy (ishbilarmonlik bo'lmagan) yozishmalarda ko'pincha kulgichlar qo'llaniladi - matn belgilarining kombinatsiyasi. Kulgichlardan foydalanish xatga jonli xarakter berishi va hatto imo-

ishoralarni almashtirishi mumkin. Ammo buni suiiste'mol qilmaslik kerak - bu yomon shakl bo'ladi. Internetda muloqot qilishda, ma'lumot berishda, his-tuyg'ularni ifodalashda yozishmalarning to'liq maxfiyiligi kutmang.

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